

**A STUDY ON IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT IN
HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT**

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Abstract

Organizations are transforming in a swift manner, the employees have to be changed according to the transformations of the organizations for getting better output. Proper Training and Developmental activities in the organizations are needed which leads to good Human Resource Development in the organizations. Modern organizations are spending junk amounts for T & D activities with an expectation of having good yields of the organizations. T & D programs are targeted to mould the employees Attitude, Skills and Knowledge towards the expectations of the organizations. Proper planning, implementing and evaluating the Training and Development programs are the important steps in T & D activities. The present study focuses on the aspects of how the T & D activities are influencing the satisfaction level and rankings of the employees in terms of aspects of T & D activities. The study comprises the samples who are employees of certain automobile companies. The results revealed that there is a significant difference between the employees who are provided with the Training in the aspects of motivation, morale, learning attitudes and satisfaction levels in the organization.

Introduction

Today the organizations are changing very swiftly. The changes are being witnessed in each and every aspect. The processes, procedures, organizational charts and material the organizations using are changing in a very quick manner. The employees will have to given clear description of what they are and what are being changed in the organizations. The employees should be given awareness of the organization. The employees have to be trained in such a manner that they should adapt themselves towards the changes happening externally and internally the organization. Training is crucial for organizational development and success. It is fruitful to both employers and employees of an organization. An employee will become more efficient and productive if he is trained well. The organizations need to focus more on Human Resource Development. The HRD can take a major leap with good Training and Development policies in the organizations. Hence the T&D has become crucial for any organization.

Training is a very important aspect in Human Resource Development. The three main aspects involved in the Training are Skills, Knowledge and Attitude. Training is being used as a tool, it is upgrading Human Resource in some organizations as a design and in many others by default.

According to **Edwin B. Flippo**, Training is the act of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for doing a particular job. Training involves the development of skills that usually necessary to perform a specific job. Its purpose is to achieve a change in the behavior of those trained and to do their jobs better. Training is necessary for new employees to them more productive also to existing employees whenever new machines, equipments and procedures are introduced. In fact, training is a continuous process.

Training consists of 8 letter TRAINING, which can be expanded as

Need for Training :

1. **Improves morale of employees-** Training helps the employee to get job security and job satisfaction. The more satisfied the employee is and the greater is his morale, the more he will contribute to organizational success and the lesser will be employee absenteeism and turnover.
2. **Less supervision-** A well trained employee will be well acquainted with the job and will need less of supervision. Thus, there will be less wastage of time and efforts.
3. **Fewer accidents-** Errors are likely to occur if the employees lack knowledge and skills required for doing a particular job. The more trained an employee is, the less are the chances of committing accidents in job and the more proficient the employee becomes.

4. **Chances of promotion-** Employees acquire skills and efficiency during training. They become more eligible for promotion. They become an asset for the organization.
5. **Increased productivity-** Training improves efficiency and productivity of employees. Well trained employees show both quantity and quality performance. There is less wastage of time, money and resources if employees are properly trained.

Training and Development caters needs of different parties and objectives of different parties. Such as

- **Individual Objectives** – help employees in achieving their personal goals, which in turn, enhances the individual contribution to an organization.
- **Organizational Objectives** – assist the organization with its primary objective by bringing individual effectiveness.
- **Functional Objectives** – maintain the department’s contribution at a level suitable to the organization’s needs.
- **Societal Objectives** – ensure that an organization is ethically and socially responsible to the needs and challenges of the society.

There are different Training methods available. They are on-the-job training methods and off-the-job training methods

On the job Training methods	Off the job Training methods
Job Rotation	Vestibule training
Job Instruction	Assessment centers
Junior boards	Role playing
Committee Assignment	Case study
Apprenticeship	Audio visual
Coaching and Counseling	Simulation
Understudy	Management games
Projects	In basket exercise
	Self study
	Lecture and Video presentation
	Management games
	Seminars and work shops
	Reading and references

Development, in contrast, is considered to be more general than training and more oriented to individual needs in addition to the organizational needs and it is the most often aimed towards

management of people. Training is a short run process which will have a specific tenure of duration but the Development is a continuous ongoing process which does not have any end time or limiting time.

Research Methodology

Need for the study

Training and Development for the organizations have become inevitable due to Rapid development in Technology and changing goals of organization. It has now been well accepted by all that training is needed by everyone in all the verticals of the organization from top to bottom. Hence there is a big need to study the aspects of need assessment of training, attitude and behavior of employees, methods of training effectiveness of training etc. However, studies on knowledge and perception of the employees about the different training programs and the effectiveness of the training in their opinion appear to be somewhat sparse.

Objectives of the study

- To analyze how far the T&D facilities can influence the performance of the employees
- To study the ranks given by the employees regarding the benefits which the organization can derive from the T&D facilities provided to them

Limitations of the study

- The present study is limited to the employees who are in Automobile industry only
- The study is conducted under certain assumptions that the information provided by all the respondents is unbiased.

Research type: Empirical

Data Sources: Primary and Secondary

Data Collection tools: Observation and Personal interview

Data Collection instrument: Well Structured questionnaire

Sample size: 100

Sample type: Convenience

Analytical tools: Percentage, Ranking method and Chi-square analysis

Data Analysis

A Well structured Questionnaire has been distributed to the selected employees in various Automobile companies in Andhra Pradesh according to the convenience and the data has been extracted from them for the purpose of the present study, the collected data has been analyzed with the help of various methods like percentage method, ranking method and the hypothesis has been tested with the help of Chi-Square analysis.

The observations are tabulated as per below.

Table showing employees expectations and Ranking with the aspects of Training and Development

Benefits	High	Medium	Low	Rank
Aware of company policies	40	36	04	I
Aware of Job	50	26	24	II
Improve in skills, knowledge and attitude	52	24	24	I
Motivation	50	50	-	I
To face new technology	58	42	-	I
Idea generation	44	38	18	III
Problem solving	68	32	-	IV
Aware of other dept's work	30	40	30	V

(Source-Questionnaire and oral interview)

Inference : From the above table, it could be inferred that, most of the employees except good benefits from the Training & Development like aware of company policies, improve in skills, knowledge & attitude, motivation and to face new technology etc.

Table showing Chi-square analysis

Ho= There is no significant relationship between employees performance and their T&D facilities in the organization

Ha=There is significant relationship between employees performance and their T&D facilities in the organizations

T & D needed /Performance	Yes	No	Total
Good	10	20	30
Poor	30	40	70
Total	40	60	100

(Source-Questionnaire and oral interview)

Degrees of freedom : (R-1)*(S-1)

(2-1)* (2-1)

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S.No	Oij	Eij	$(Oij-Eij)^2$	$(Oij-Eij)^2/Eij$
1	10	18	64	3.556
2	20	9	121	13.444
3	40	28	144	5.142
4	30	42	144	4.8
Total				26.952

Inference : At 5% confidence level, chi-square table value is 3.84. As the calculated Chi-Square value is greater than the book value, the Null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is significant relationship between employees' performance and T&D facilities in the organization.

Conclusion

Today the organizations are implementing modern training methods to help in boosting the self morale of the employees at work places. Present study revealed the same factor, i.e. there is a significant relationship between the employees' performance and the T&D in the organizations. If the employees were provided with the better T&D opportunities, they would learn the new procedures and they perform well in their jobs. It is also concluded that the T&D facilities will be majorly influencing the Motivation, Morale level of the employees, improves attitude, knowledge, skills and behavior of the employees and also helps in knowing the new technologies which inturn helps the organizations in achieving the short term and long term objectives

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